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Research Article

**EPIDEMIOLOGY OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA AMONG
PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN IN BURAYDAH**¹Asma Mutni al-Mutairi

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Background: Asthma is a one of the most widely spread chronic disease in children that can cause a significant co-morbidity illness. Until now, no data available to estimate the prevalence of asthma in Buraydah, Saudi Arabia.

Objective: This study aims to estimate the prevalence rate and the epidemiological characteristics of bronchial asthma among primary school children in Buraydah, Saudi Arabia.

Method: A cross-sectional descriptive study will be conducted in general primary Buraydah schools, by using pre-tested, well-constructed self-administered standardized and validated Arabic version questionnaire, which will be directly to parents of students or guardians.

Result

The prevalence of Asthma in our study was 29.1% among children whose age between 5 and 15 years in Qassim Region.

Conclusions

The prevalence of Bronchial asthma in Buraydah is higher than those reported in other local areas.

Key words: Asthma, children, epidemiology, Buraydah, Saudi Arabia

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INTRODUCTION:

During the last decades, the increasing incidence of chronic allergic diseases in children and adolescent groups had been associated with increased incidence in morbidity and mortality (1)(2)(3). These chronic allergic diseases are considered the most common cause of school absence among children all over the world. Not only that but also these diseases affect the child's life in different ways (4). According to the WHO reports, 235 million people currently suffer from asthma, so it's considered as the top of the chronic allergic disease.

Asthma is a heterogeneous disease characterized by chronic airway inflammation. It is defined by the history of respiratory symptoms that include wheeze, shortness of breath, chest tightness and cough that vary over time and in intensity, together with variable expiratory airflow limitation (5). Bronchial asthma is multi-factorial disease, which include genetic, triggers like common cold and exercise, and environmental factors all together contribute in developing this disease (3).

There are many published epidemiological studies of asthma in Saudi Arabia. The Saudi initiative for asthma (2016) reported increasing prevalence among Saudi adults (6). Al-Frayh showed an increase in the prevalence of asthma from 8 % in 1986 in Jeddah and Riyadh (costal humid and desert dry, respectively) to 23 % in 1995 in Jizan and Hail (costal humid and desert dry, respectively) among schoolchildren aged 6 to 18 years.

The impact of gender on asthma prevalence and incidence was reported in many studies. Prevalence of asthma is more common in boys than in girls during childhood (7)(8). Asthma is the most frequent cause of emergency room visits and hospital admissions (9).

More than seventy five percent of children who develop asthma symptoms before age 7 were no longer have symptoms by age 16 (3). However, asthma can develop at any age, including adolescent (3).

In Saudi Arabia, many studies were conducted to investigate certain aspects of this disease, including prevalence among children (4) (10) (11) (12)(13). However, and to the best of the investigators' knowledge, no study was conducted to estimate the

prevalence of bronchial asthma among primary school children in Buraydah City. There are limited data on the epidemiology of allergic disorders in Al-Qassim Region. Such data are needed for, amongst other things, helping to plan service provision at a time when there is considerable investment taking place in national healthcare development.

This study aimed to determine the prevalence rate and to define the epidemiological characteristics of bronchial asthma among primary school children in Buraydah, Saudi Arabia.

METHODS:**Study Setting**

This study was conducted in Buraydah. Buraydah city is the capital of Al-Qassim Region in Saudi Arabia, its geographical coordinates are 26° 19' 54" North, 43° 58' 18" East. It has a population of 614,093. There are around 168 general primary schools and 35284 students in total.

Study population

The population was all 35284 schoolchildren in the general primary schools in Buraydah, Saudi Arabia.

Study duration

The study was conducted in the period from 25th March 2018 to 25th April 2018.

Inclusion Criteria

All Students in general primary schools in Buraydah, including resident students, were enrolled in this study. Age was from six to twelve years.

Exclusion Criteria

Any child with a history of chronic pulmonary disease, systemic diseases other than bronchial asthma and vertebral/costal deformity, or neuromuscular disease were excluded.

Study design, sampling technique and sample size

This study was a descriptive cross-sectional with a representative sample among primary school children in Buraydah. The sample size was calculated using OpenEpi.com. The prevalence in Buraydah is unknown, but a guess estimate was about 50% positive and 50% negative. If the result is 50%, within 95% confidence level the true frequency lies between 45 and 55%. The minimal sample size will be 380. The sample size was also estimated by using this equation

$$n = \frac{z^2 p(p - 1)}{d^2}$$

where Z = 1.96 for confidence interval 95%,
P= expected probability which will be 15% (14)
d= margin of error which will be 5%.

The minimal final sample size was 196. Thus 400 were finally selected. A cluster sampling was used based on gender and school location. Then in each school, stratified sampling was used based on grade. Simple random sampling was finally used to select students in each class. We assured the randomization by using the Random Number Generator to create a list of random numbers.

In this study the criteria to define asthma was The Saudi Initiative for Asthma Group (SINA)

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT:

A pre-tested, well-constructed self-administered Arabic version questionnaire was used to collect information directly from parents. The questionnaire was previously standardized and validated to the Saudi Community. It contains questions on history and family history of atopic asthma, environmental asthma exposure to animals, tobacco, and use of medication of asthma (15).

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

Both the health directorate of Qassim region and the Education Department of qssim approved this study.

Children parent signed an informed before reading the questionnaire.

Statistical processing and data analysis

Data was first entered into Microsoft Excel and then imported and analyzed using SPSS “Statistical Package of Social Science 24” (SPSS version 24). Nominal, ordinal and dichotomous variables were expressed as frequency (%). Association was tested using the Chi-square or Fisher exact tests when necessary. Continuous variables were tested for normal distribution and then parametric tests were used and expressed as mean and standard deviation. The cutoff for statistical significance was a p-value of 0.05.

RESULTS:

A total of 309 students’ parents responded to our questionnaire. A hundred and fifty seven (50.8%) students were male and 152 (49.2%) were female with a male to female ratio of 1:1. The age of children ranges from 5 to 15 years with a mean of 9.5 (1.8) and a median of 10 years. Students’ academic achievement and residence status is illustrated in table 1.

Table 1: demographic characteristics of the participants (n= 309).

		Male		Female		Total		P value
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	
Age mean (SD)		9.4 (1.8)		9.7 (1.8)		9.5 (1.8)		0.153
Student grade	1.00	28	17.8%	17	11.2%	45	14.6%	0.413
	2.00	29	18.5%	22	14.5%	51	16.5%	
	3.00	21	13.4%	20	13.2%	41	13.3%	
	4.00	22	14.0%	26	17.1%	48	15.5%	
	5.00	27	17.2%	35	23.0%	62	20.1%	
	6.00	30	19.1%	32	21.1%	62	20.1%	
Duration of residency in your city	less than 5 years	7	4.5%	7	4.6%	14	4.5%	0.293
	5 to 10 years	106	67.5%	90	59.2%	196	63.4%	
	more than 10 years	44	28.0%	55	36.2%	99	32.0%	
Moved from your city (last 6 months)	Yes	19	12.2%	24	15.9%	43	14.0%	0.348
	No	137	87.8%	127	84.1%	264	86.0%	

Regarding the prevalence of BA-related symptoms, 124 (40.1%) children experienced wheezing in their lives. Half of them (19.4%) experienced less than 4 attacks of wheezing in the last year and only 1% reported more than 12 attacks during the same period. Forty eight (15%) children experienced the first attack of wheezing between 1 to 2 years of age.

Around one-third (36.9%) of the students had history of seasonal increase of wheezing attacks. The prevalence of exercise-induced wheeze was 24.8% among students. There was no statistically significant difference in prevalence of BA-related symptoms between boys and girls as shown in table 2.

Table 2: association of wheezing with gender among our participants (n=309).

		Male		Female		Total		P value
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	
History of wheezing	Yes	65	41.4%	59	38.8%	124	40.1%	0.643
	No	92	58.6%	93	61.2%	185	59.9%	
Age at first wheezing attack	None	92	58.6%	93	61.2%	185	59.9%	0.146
	Before age one year	8	5.1%	17	11.2%	25	8.1%	
	between age 1-2 years	30	19.1%	18	11.8%	48	15.5%	
	between age 3-4 years	15	9.6%	11	7.2%	26	8.4%	
	after age 4 years	12	7.6%	13	8.6%	25	8.1%	
Last wheezing attack	None	92	58.6%	92	60.5%	184	59.5%	0.787
	less than one month	19	12.1%	22	14.5%	41	13.3%	
	1-12 months	21	13.4%	19	12.5%	40	12.9%	
	more than 12 months	25	15.9%	19	12.5%	44	14.2%	
frequency of wheezing attacks (last 12 months)	None	118	75.2%	105	69.1%	223	72.2%	0.204
	less than 4 attacks	31	19.7%	29	19.1%	60	19.4%	
	4-12 attacks	7	4.5%	16	10.5%	23	7.4%	
	more than 12 attacks	1	0.6%	2	1.3%	3	1.0%	
wheezing attacks increase (seasonally)	Yes	58	36.9%	60	39.5%	118	38.2%	0.647
	No	99	63.1%	92	60.5%	191	61.8%	
History of wheezing attack after exercise	Yes	39	24.8%	29	19.1%	68	22.0%	0.222
	No	118	75.2%	123	80.9%	241	78.0%	
Wheezing after exercise (Last attack)	None	116	73.9%	118	77.6%	234	75.7%	0.064
	less than one month	8	5.1%	12	7.9%	20	6.5%	
	1 to 12 months	10	6.4%	13	8.6%	23	7.4%	
	more than 12 months	23	14.6%	8	5.3%	31	10.0%	

Breathlessness and tightness were experienced by a third (32%) of the children and around half of them (14.6%) had their last attack in the last month. Almost the same number (14.9%) had their attack in the period between 1 and 12 months. Frequency of

cough and bronchitis is shown in table 3. Half of children (49.5%) experienced rhinitis attacks with a significantly higher frequency among boys (55.4%) than among girls (43.4%), $p=0.035$.

Table 3: association of breathlessness, bronchitis, and rhinitis with gender among our participants (n=309).

		Male		Female		Total		P Value
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	
History of breathlessness/ tightness	Yes	54	34.4%	47	30.9%	101	32.7%	0.515
	No	103	65.6%	105	69.1%	208	67.3%	
breathlessness or tightness (Last attack)	None	92	58.6%	93	61.2%	185	59.9%	0.266
	less than one month	22	14.0%	23	15.1%	45	14.6%	
	1 to 12 months	21	13.4%	25	16.4%	46	14.9%	
	more than 12 months	22	14.0%	11	7.2%	33	10.7%	
History of frequent dry cough at Night	Yes	33	21.0%	41	27.0%	74	23.9%	0.220
	No	124	79.0%	111	73.0%	235	76.1%	
Dry cough at Night (Last attack)	None	124	79.0%	111	73.0%	235	76.1%	0.109
	less than one month	16	10.2%	29	19.1%	45	14.6%	
	1 to 12 months	10	6.4%	5	3.3%	15	4.9%	
	more than 12 months	7	4.5%	7	4.6%	14	4.5%	
History of bronchitis treatment (last two year)	Yes	43	27.4%	49	32.2%	92	29.8%	0.351
	No	114	72.6%	103	67.8%	217	70.2%	
history of Eczema	Yes	32	20.4%	38	25.0%	70	22.7%	0.332
	No	125	79.6%	114	75.0%	239	77.3%	
History of Rhinitis attacks	Yes	87	55.4%	66	43.4%	153	49.5%	0.035
	No	70	44.6%	86	56.6%	156	50.5%	

Ninety (29.1%) students were previously diagnosed as asthmatic. Details of previous attacks and medication are shown in table 4. Nineteen (6.1%) of the students started using asthma medications in the last month and almost the same percentage 6.8% started in the last year with a significant difference

between boys and girls ($p \leq 0.001$). Likewise, the frequency of medicinal course in the last 12 months was significantly different between boys and girls ($p=0.008$). The frequency of drug usage is illustrated in table 4.

Table 4: association of asthma with gender among our participants (n=309).

		Male		Female		Total		P value
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	
History of Asthma (Diagnosed by doctor)	Yes	43	27.4%	47	30.9%	90	29.1%	0.494
	No	114	72.6%	105	69.1%	219	70.9%	
Age when asthma diagnosed	None	114	72.6%	105	69.1%	219	70.9%	0.417
	Less than one-year age	15	9.6%	15	9.9%	30	9.7%	
	1 to 2 years of age	10	6.4%	19	12.5%	29	9.4%	
	3 to 4 years of ages	13	8.3%	9	5.9%	22	7.1%	
	after 5 years of ages	5	3.2%	4	2.6%	9	2.9%	
Asthma (last attach)	None	114	72.6%	105	69.1%	219	70.9%	0.511
	less than one month	20	12.7%	26	17.1%	46	14.9%	
	1 to 6 months	10	6.4%	11	7.2%	21	6.8%	
	7 to12 months	3	1.9%	5	3.3%	8	2.6%	
	more than 12 months	10	6.4%	5	3.3%	15	4.9%	
frequency of asthma attacks (last 12 months)	None	117	74.5%	113	74.3%	230	74.4%	0.337
	less than 4 attacks	26	16.6%	23	15.1%	49	15.9%	
	4-12 attacks	12	7.6%	9	5.9%	21	6.8%	
	more than 12 attacks	2	1.3%	7	4.6%	9	2.9%	
Asthma medication use	Yes	37	23.6%	41	27.0%	78	25.2%	0.491
	No	120	76.4%	111	73.0%	231	74.8%	
Start of Medication use for Asthma	None	120	76.4%	111	73.0%	231	74.8%	0.000
	In the last month	7	4.5%	12	7.9%	19	6.1%	
	1 to 12 months ago	3	1.9%	18	11.8%	21	6.8%	
	more than 12 months ago.	27	17.2%	11	7.2%	38	12.3%	
frequency of medicine course (last 12 months)	Daily	9	5.7%	2	1.3%	11	3.6%	0.008
	More than once per month.	6	3.8%	19	12.5%	25	8.1%	
	Less than once per month.	19	12.1%	15	9.9%	34	11.0%	
	None at all.	123	78.3%	116	76.3%	239	77.3%	

Exposure to smoking at home in the last month was reported among 42 (13.6%) children. The frequency of exposure was significantly more among girls' homes than among boys' (18.4% versus 8.9% respectively, $p = 0.015$). Pets were present in 12.9% of the children's homes. The majority were cats and birds (10.4%). Around 28% of the children a nearby garden as illustrated in table 5. The prevalence of asthma among fathers, mothers, and siblings were 18.8%, 17.2%, 27.8%, respectively with no significant difference between males and females. However, grandparents' history of Eczema was

significantly higher among girls' families than boys' (15.1% versus 6.4%, $p=0.013$). Age, duration of residency in the city, indoors smoking by a family member or in children's homes, and pets in the house were not significantly associated with previous history of asthma as shown in table 6. Nevertheless, the presence of Prosopis tree (*Prosopis juliflora*) near the house was significantly associated with history of asthma ($P = 0.016$). Almost a quarter of the asthmatic children (24.4%) lived near Prosopis tree while only 13.2% of nonasthmatic did not.

Table 5: association of respiratory risk/aggravating factors with gender among our participants (n=309).

		Male		Female		Total		P value
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	
Smoking status (Indoor etc..)	Yes	14	8.9%	28	18.4%	42	13.6%	0.015
	No	143	91.1%	124	81.6%	267	86.4%	
Cigarettes (number)	None smoker	145	92.4%	125	82.2%	270	87.4%	0.143
	Less than 5 cigarettes	4	2.5%	8	5.3%	12	3.9%	
	10 cigarettes	4	2.5%	9	5.9%	13	4.2%	
	20 cigarettes	3	1.9%	7	4.6%	10	3.2%	
	40 cigarettes	1	0.6%	1	0.7%	2	0.6%	
	More than 40 cigarettes	0	0.0%	2	1.3%	2	0.6%	
Family smoking status	None	145	92.4%	124	81.6%	269	87.1%	0.113
	Brother	3	1.9%	5	3.3%	8	2.6%	
	Father	8	5.1%	17	11.2%	25	8.1%	
	Father & brother	0	0.0%	1	0.7%	1	0.3%	
	Grand	1	0.6%	1	0.7%	2	0.6%	
	Cousin	0	0.0%	1	0.7%	1	0.3%	
	Uncle	0	0.0%	3	2.0%	3	1.0%	
Pets in the house	Yes	21	13.4%	19	12.5%	40	12.9%	0.819
	No	136	86.6%	133	87.5%	269	87.1%	
Pets type	No pets	136	86.6%	131	86.2%	267	86.4%	0.642
	Dog	0	0.0%	1	0.7%	1	0.3%	
	Cat & Birds	16	10.2%	16	10.5%	32	10.4%	
	Another animal.	5	3.2%	3	2.0%	8	2.6%	
Garden near or in the house	Yes	42	26.8%	44	28.9%	86	27.8%	0.667
	No	115	73.2%	108	71.1%	223	72.2%	
Prosopis tree near the House	Yes	25	15.9%	26	17.1%	51	16.5%	0.780
	No	132	84.1%	126	82.9%	258	83.5%	
AC type	Freon	154	98.1%	131	86.2%	285	92.2%	0.000
	water cooling type	3	1.9%	21	13.8%	24	7.8%	
Frequency of changing/cleaning AC filter	once every year	89	56.7%	98	64.5%	187	60.5%	0.162
	another interval	68	43.3%	54	35.5%	122	39.5%	

Table 6: association of asthma status (diagnosed by doctor) and possible risk factors among our participants (n=309).

		Asthma diagnosed by doctor				P value
		Yes		No		
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	
	Age mean (SD)	9.2 (1.78)		9.6 (1.89)		0.055
Duration of residency in your city	less than 5 years	2	2.2%	12	5.5%	0.057
	5 to 10 years	66	73.3%	130	59.4%	
	more than 10 years	22	24.4%	77	35.2%	
Age at first wheezing attack	None	19	21.1%	166	75.8%	0.000
	before one year	17	18.9%	8	3.7%	
	between 1-2 year	28	31.1%	20	9.1%	
	between 3-4	17	18.9%	9	4.1%	
	after 4 year	9	10.0%	16	7.3%	
History of wheezing attack after exercise	yes	44	48.9%	24	11.0%	0.000
	no	46	51.1%	195	89.0%	
Smoking status (Indoor etc..)	yes	12	13.3%	30	13.7%	0.932
	no	78	86.7%	189	86.3%	
Pets in the house	yes	14	15.6%	26	11.9%	0.381
	no	76	84.4%	193	88.1%	
presence of garden near or in the House	yes	29	32.2%	57	26.0%	0.270
	no	61	67.8%	162	74.0%	
presence of Prosopis tree near the House	yes	22	24.4%	29	13.2%	0.016
	no	68	75.6%	190	86.8%	

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of Asthma in this study was 29.1% among children whose age between 5 and 15 years in Qassim Region. This percentage is almost triple the 10% reported by *Khawaji et al.* among children in Jazan Region (17). This might be related to the difference of the geographic nature of both regions. Qassim is a well-known mixed agricultural region where a higher number of trees and plants are observed especially Prosopis trees. Millions species of Prosopis tree were implanted in some parts of KSA as roadside embellishment. *Al-Frayh et al.* confirmed the role of Prosopis pollen as a sensitizing factor in KSA among many multiple sensitive patients especially in Qassim Region (16). Of the respondents in our study, 16.5% confirmed the presence of Prosopis tree near their houses. Similar to *Al-Frayh et al.* report, a significant relationship was confirmed between history of asthma and the presence of Prosopis tree (*Prosopis juliflora*) near the house ($p = 0.016$). However, the presence of a garden in or near the house did not significantly increase the prevalence of asthma ($p=0.270$). Likewise, no

increase of prevalence was found in relation to the presence of pets in the house ($p=0.381$).

In contradistinction to this study, *Hamam et al.* in their findings from Taif Area in KSA, reported that indoors allergens such as smoking of a family member had an association with history of asthma. In This study there was no association between smoking indoors by a family member and asthma (17).

Nearly 40% reported seasonal increase of wheezing attacks. This might be related to the increased occurrence of dust storms during season and a probable reason of the prevalence of asthma in Qassim region than others because dust storms in Qassim are more frequent.

Similar to *Hamam et al.* asthma prevalence, in our study, was higher among girls (30.9%) than among boys (27.4%), however there was no statistical significance in both reports. Asthma was found to be more prevalent among boys than girls in several North American and Indian studies (18, 19, 20). In the current study, the prevalence of exercise-induced wheeze and wheeze during the last 12 months was

22% and 26.2%, respectively. This figure is higher than that reported by *Khawaji et al.* where they reported exercise-induced asthma and wheeze in the past year as 14.7% and 11.4%, respectively. The physiologic response to exercise usually results in slight bronchodilation in normal population (21). However, asthmatic patients without anti-inflammatory treatment may experience an asthma attack provoked by exercise (22). Airway dehydration, resulting from increased ventilation of cold or dry air during exercise is a probable cause (23). In the current study, around half (48.9%) of asthmatic students experienced wheezing attacks after exercise (exercise-induced asthma, EIA). On the other hand, 11% of nonasthmatic children had history of wheezing attacks after exercise (exercise-induced bronchoconstriction, EIB) ($p = 0.001$) (24).

CONCLUSION:

Simple and non-invasive methods were used to screen asthma. The prevalence of asthma (29.1%) among school children in Buraydah was a little higher compared to other local regions. One of the important reasons for this higher prevalence is that Buraydah is a known agricultural region. Early intervention and close observation are needed to limit the asthma attack.

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